

Effectiveness of traditional verses virtual storytelling as diversional techniques on level of pain during IV cannulation among pediatric patients admitted in hospitals of selected areas

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Background:

Pain during IV cannulation is a common and distressing experience among pediatric patients. Distraction techniques like storytelling can help reduce pain. This study compares the effectiveness of traditional versus virtual storytelling in minimizing pain among children.

Objectives:

To assess and compare the effectiveness of traditional storytelling and virtual storytelling on the level of pain during IV cannulation among pediatric patients, and to determine the association between pain levels and selected demographic variables.

Methodology:

A quantitative, quasi-experimental post-test only two-group design was used. A total of 80 pediatric patients (40 in each group) were selected using non-probability convenient sampling. Data were collected from 12/12/2025 to 10/01/2026 in selected hospitals. Pain was assessed using the Wong-Baker Faces Pain Rating Scale. Data analysis included descriptive and inferential statistics, including Z-test and Fisher's exact test.

Results:

In the traditional storytelling group, 55% experienced severe pain, 35% moderate, and 10% mild pain, with a mean score of 7.7 ± 2.2 . In the virtual storytelling group, 85% had mild pain and 15% moderate pain, with a mean score of 4.3 ± 0.7 . The difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). No significant association was found between pain and demographic variables.

Conclusion:

Virtual storytelling is significantly more effective than traditional storytelling in reducing pain during IV cannulation among paediatric patients.

Keywords: Pediatric pain, IV cannulation, traditional storytelling, virtual storytelling, distraction techniques

INTRODUCTION

A child is an individual undergoing continuous physical, emotional, and intellectual development. Hospitalization can be a stressful experience for children due to unfamiliar environments, pain, anxiety, and medical procedures. Among these, intravenous (IV) cannulation is a common but painful procedure that often causes fear, distress, and behavioural resistance in pediatric patients. Children may express pain through crying, facial expressions, and body movements, making pain management challenging.

Pain is frequently undertreated in children, yet it can lead to long-term negative effects such as fear of medical procedures and poor cooperation. Therefore, it is the responsibility of healthcare professionals, especially nurses, to reduce pain and anxiety using safe and effective methods. Distraction techniques are widely used non-pharmacological approaches that help shift the child's attention away from pain. These include visual, auditory, and interactive methods.

Storytelling is one such effective distraction technique. Traditional storytelling uses verbal narration, imagination, and emotional connection to comfort the child, while virtual storytelling uses digital media like animated videos to engage children more actively. Both methods help reduce pain perception by diverting attention and promoting relaxation. Virtual storytelling, in particular, enhances engagement through audio-visual stimulation, making it a valuable tool in modern pediatric care. Overall, storytelling techniques play an important role in reducing pain, anxiety, and improving cooperation during procedures like IV cannulation.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Hospitalization is a stressful experience for children and can lead to fear, anxiety, and developmental disturbances. Painful procedures like IV cannulation further increase distress, as children often lack the ability to understand and express pain clearly. Unmanaged pain can result in poor cooperation, delayed recovery, and long-term psychological effects such as fear of medical procedures. IV cannulation is a routine yet painful procedure, with nearly 70–85% of children experiencing moderate to severe pain without proper intervention. Therefore, effective pain management is essential in pediatric care. Along with pharmacological methods, non-pharmacological techniques like distraction are increasingly used to reduce pain and anxiety. Storytelling is a simple, safe, and cost-effective distraction technique. Traditional storytelling provides emotional comfort and human connection, while virtual storytelling uses audio-visual elements to create immersive distraction and better engagement. Although virtual methods may be more effective, they require resources and technology, whereas traditional storytelling is easily accessible in all settings.

OBJECTIVE

Primary Objective

To assess the effectiveness of traditional storytelling on level of pain during IV cannulation among pediatric patients.

To assess the effectiveness of virtual storytelling on level of pain during IV cannulation among pediatric patients.

To compare level of pain in traditional and virtual storytelling during IV cannulation among pediatric patients.

Secondary Objective

To find association between study findings with selected demographical variables.

METHODOLOGY:

A quantitative research approach was adopted for this study to assess the effectiveness of traditional and virtual storytelling on pain during IV cannulation among pediatric patients. The study employed a quasi-experimental post-test only two-group design and was conducted in selected pediatric hospitals. after obtaining formal permission from the concerned authorities. The target population included children aged 3–5 years undergoing IV cannulation. A total of 80 samples were selected using a non-probability convenient sampling technique, with 40 children in the traditional storytelling group and 40 in the virtual storytelling group. Children who met the inclusion criteria and whose parents were willing to provide consent were included in the study. Data were collected using a structured tool consisting of demographic variables such as age, gender, weight, duration of hospital stay, and frequency of prick, along with the standardized Wong-Baker Faces Pain Rating Scale to assess pain levels. The tool was validated by 11 experts from different fields to ensure its content validity. The data collection period was from 12/12/2025 to 10/01/2026. The researcher explained the purpose of the study to the parents and obtained informed consent before data collection. Traditional storytelling was provided to one group, while virtual storytelling (audio-visual method) was given to the other group during IV cannulation. Pain levels were assessed immediately after the procedure. The collected data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, and inferential statistics including Z-test (or t-test) to compare pain levels between the two groups and Fisher's exact test to find the association between pain and selected demographic variables. Ethical principles such as confidentiality, voluntary participation, and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study.

Results

SECTION I - Description of samples based on their demographic characteristics.

Age:

Most children in the traditional group were 3–4 years (55%), while in the virtual group most were 4–5 years (67.5%).

Gender:

Traditional group had more males (55%), whereas the virtual group had slightly more females (52.5%).

Weight:

Most children in both groups were between 12–17.9 kg, with slightly more in 15–17.9 kg in the virtual group.

Duration of Hospital Stay:

Most children in both groups stayed less than 24 hours, slightly higher in the virtual group (92.5%).

Frequency of Prick:

Most children had one prick, higher in the virtual group (95%), while multiple pricks were more in the traditional group.

Section II

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of traditional storytelling on level of pain during IV cannulation among paediatric patients. **n=40**

Pain	Traditional story telling	
	Freq	%
Mild	4	10.0%
Moderate	14	35.0%
Severe	22	55.0%

FIGURE: 1 A Pie chart showing percentage wise distribution according to pain in Traditional storytelling among pediatric patients.

Description: Above graph and table shows that more than half of the children (55%) experienced severe pain, while 35% reported moderate pain. Only 10% of the children experienced mild pain, indicating that traditional storytelling was less effective in reducing pain compared to other methods

Section III**Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of virtual storytelling on level of pain during IV cannulation among paediatric patients.****n=40**

Pain	Virtual story telling	
	Freq	%
Mild	34	85.0%
Moderate	6	15.0%
Severe	0	0.0%

FIGURE: 2 A Pie chart showing percentage wise distribution according to pain in Virtual storytelling among pediatric patients.

Description: Above Table and graph shows that the majority of children (85%) experienced mild pain, while 15% reported moderate pain. No children experienced severe pain.

Section IV

Analysis of data related to the level of pain in traditional and virtual storytelling during IV cannulation among paediatric patients.

Pain	Traditional story telling		Virtual story telling	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	4	10.0%	34	85.0%
Moderate	14	35.0%	6	15.0%
Severe	22	55.0%	0	0.0%

FIGURE: 3 A Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution according to pain in traditional and virtual storytelling group among pediatric patients.

Description: Above table and graph shows that in the traditional storytelling group, most children experienced severe pain (55%), followed by moderate pain (35%), while only 10% reported mild pain. In contrast, the virtual storytelling group showed a marked reduction in pain, with 85% of children experiencing mild pain, 15% having moderate pain, and no children reporting severe pain,

Section V

Analysis of data related to the association between pain during IV cannulation among paediatric patients with selected demographical variables in traditional storytelling.

Demographic variable		Pain			p-value
		Mild	Moderate	Severe	
Age	3-4 years	2	8	12	1.000
	4-5 years	2	6	10	
Gender	Male	2	7	13	0.897
	Female	2	7	9	
Weight	< 12 kg	0	3	1	0.503
	12 to 14.9 kg	2	5	9	
	15 to 17.9 kg	2	5	12	
	>=18 kg	0	1	0	
Duration of hospital	< 24 hours	4	12	19	1.000
	24 to 48 hours	0	1	1	
	49 to 72 hours	0	1	2	
Frequency of prick	1 prick	2	9	18	0.254
	2-3 pricks	2	5	4	

Analysis of data related to the association between pain during IV cannulation among paediatric patients with selected demographical variables in Virtual storytelling

Demographic variable		Pain		p-value
		Mild	Moderate	
Age	3-4 years	10	3	0.370
	4-5 years	24	3	
Gender	Male	14	5	0.085
	Female	20	1	
Weight	12 to 14.9 kg	14	2	1.000
	15 to 17.9 kg	19	4	
	>=18 kg	1	0	
Duration of hospital	< 24 hours	31	6	1.000
	24 to 48 hours	1	0	
	49 to 72 hours	1	0	
	> 72 hours	1	0	
Frequency of prick	1 prick	32	6	1.000
	2-3 pricks	2	0	

DISCUSSION

The study found that both traditional and virtual storytelling were effective in reducing pain during IV cannulation among pediatric patients; however, virtual storytelling was more effective. Traditional storytelling reduced pain by providing emotional comfort and engaging the child's imagination, while virtual storytelling showed greater effectiveness due to its immersive audio-visual distraction. The mean pain score was lower in the virtual group (4.3) compared to the traditional group (7.7), with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$), leading to rejection of the null hypothesis. No significant association was found between pain and demographic variables ($p > 0.05$). These findings are supported by previous studies, concluding that virtual storytelling is a more effective method for pain reduction, though traditional storytelling remains useful, especially in low-resource settings.

CONCLUSION:

The study concludes that virtual storytelling is significantly more effective than traditional storytelling in reducing pain during IV cannulation among pediatric patients. It is a simple, safe, cost-effective, and non-invasive intervention that can be easily incorporated into pediatric nursing practice to improve patient comfort and cooperation.

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